

A Study on Security Issues in E-Mail Communication

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Abstract

Today, the entire life of human being involves in facing of risk in their day to day life from the technological advancements. An increasing number of technological advancement in internet world, the domestic and international criminal activities has been increased. Computer and other electronic devices can be a tool to commit crime or are targeted by criminals such as hackers. The article presents the role of hackers in electronic mail and intention with their way of thinking, planning and performing attacks for their personal gain and as well as others grow up. We mainly focused on how hacking works in E-mail and its impact in India.

Keywords: Importance of E-mail, Methodologies in E-mail Communication, Security issues behind E-mail, Security threats in E-mail, Methods behind hacking of an E-mail, LAW and Punishments.

Introduction

People all over the world have ability to communicate with each other by E-Mails, Weblogs, Cell phones, Texting message and other technological advancements. People do this in hope that they are securing their life by preparing for reduce the level of depression. The communication often leads to real-life, physical conflicts as well as feelings of depression, hopelessness and loss.

Moreover when it is unclear or fake it can lead to misunderstanding in their personal life. The people can become a victim from their movements, due to the desire of using modern technology and their failure to use safe internet practices or by a professional computer hacker.

Importance of E-mail

The most commonly referred and preferred mode of electronic communication is Electronic mail or E-mail. Almost all internet users have a minimum of one E-mail account each and an average of three different E-mail accounts per person.

E-mail allows people to stay in touch with relatives and share movements of joy and sorrow, transfer important documents, forward meaningless junk to friends, play tricks and even maintain conditional

business deals, all within a matter of seconds. More and more individuals and organizations depending upon e-mail for their daily dose of critical communication, some of which may contain personal information, company secrets and sensitive information. Because of it's an importance E-mail hacking is involve in different methods.

Methodologies in E-Mail Communication

The E-mail service works much like a post office, it allows to send, receive and forward messages. There are many similarities used between E-mails and physical mail. The “header” is who and where it is addressed to. The “body” is the message sent. The “envelope” is how it gets there. There needs to be at least one “post office” like mail server that can send and receive the E-mail. Also, there is a “weight” limit on what sender can send. For “heavy” E-mails, such as sending large files or a lot of pictures, the sender needs to use a second service to “carry” the E-mail package.

There are 3 major protocols used in E-mail,

- SMTP (Simple Mail Transfer Protocol): for sending E-mails and the standard for any E-mail server or client for sending new E-mails to others.
- POP3 (Post Office Protocol 3): for receiving E-mails and was the first to be widely adopted for E-mail server. POP3 will download any messages it sees on the E-mail server onto the receiver device, whether it be the computer or phone
- IMAP (Internet Message Access Protocol): This is used for coordinating the status of E-mail such as read, deleted and moved across multiple E-mail clients. It is quicker to see new E-mails and it synchronized with the server.

A. Sending E-mail: To send an E-mail, sender must have their identification address. Usually this is formatted as such: support@ieee.com. “Support” is the user name of the recipient and “@ieee.com” is the domain where the user has their E-mail hosted. The sender “address” the E-mail to the receiver, the E-mail server knows where to send it. The E-mail server will talk to the other E-mail server and ask if there is an account with that E-mail. If there is, the E-mail server will then “deliver” that E-mail to the right person or the receiver.

B. Receiving E-mail: To receive E-mail, the E-mail client must be configure properly and have either POP3 or IMAP enabled on the server. Usually, all servers have POP3 enabled by default. It is sufficient to receive the E-mail. Once someone sends an E-mail, the server will accept the E-mail into its “mail spooler”. The mail spooler is the catch all area that then sorts out the E-mail to which user it should deliver it to. The transactions can be done over network of networks as mentioned in Figure1.

Security issues behind E-mail

Although the E-mail is now most widely used mode of internet electronic communication it is not the safest and most reliable. Virus infected e-mails and wiretapping on network lines are the main reasons that affect the reliability of internet E-mail communication.

At this stage, it is an important to point out the insecurity in the internet E-mail delivery pathway:

- WebMail: If the connection in WebMail server is “insecure” such as the address is http:// and NOT https://, then all information including username and password is not encrypted as it passes between the WebMail server and the client.
- SMTP: For communication if the mail server requests to send username and password to “login” to the SMTP server in order to relay messages to other servers, the server sends in plain text and does not encrypt the messages. It insecure for E-mail user.
- POP and IMAP: The protocols require sending username and password to login, these credentials are not encrypted. So, the messages and credentials can be read by any eavesdropper.

- **BACKUPS:** E-mail messages are generally stored on SMTP servers in plain unencrypted text. Backups of the data on these servers may be made at any time and administrators can read any of the data on these machines and may be read by unknown persons as a result.

Security threats in E-mail

E-mail and mail system are also targets of attackers. Attackers can exploit e-mail to gain control over an organization, access confidential information, or disrupt IT access to resources using treats. Some common E-Mail threats are explained below.

- **Snooping:** is unauthorized access to E-mail messages including user ids and passwords are transmitted between computers and E-mail servers as plain text. This is not secure and anyone who can intercept this can read sender's E-mail and obtain user ids, passwords and sensitive E-mail content.
- **E-Mail Spam:** Spam is flooding the internet with many copies of unsolicited bulk E-mail messages. Spam E-mails are usually commercial advertisements like replica watches, cheap drugs, get rich quick and other dubious products. Spam E-mails decreases productivity and increases the cost of E-mail use. Many legitimate E-mails are also filtered by spam filters.
- **E-mail Viruses and Worms:** Many viruses and worms are spread as attachment of E-mails. Once the computer is infected, the Viruses and Worms may spread into network computers. These viruses can send private information to attackers.

Even if the E-mail server is equipped with strong anti-virus application and spam filters to stop spam, viruses, and other unwanted content the hacker reaches the network infrastructure and E-mail users with incredible programming knowledge and their motivations.

Methods behind hacking of an E-mail

There are numerous methods behind hacking of an E-mail account on Local and Wide Area Networks. Very Common, All the methods capture E-mail ID and password in different ways. The following common methods are used by the hackers.

- **Method 1:** Sending a mail containing false info and asks them to mention their username and password in the reply to get the access into that service which mentioned in mail like Fake mail.
- **Method 2:** Capturing and sending every keystroke of the victim computer from keyboard to the hacker is called keylogging. A professional hacker writing his own keylogger for E-mail hacking.
- **Method 3:** One of the best methods of E-mail hacking is cookie stealing. This method stores cookie is used by web server to identify and authenticate the user.
- **Method 4:** Hacker creates a web page of the login form which exactly looks like the E-mail service. Then they hosting it on a public server and send it to users via E-mail to capture E-mail ID and password is called phishing.
- **Method 5:** This allows a remote "operator" to control an E-mail system like Remote Administration Tool.
- **Method 6:** A hacker creates and executes their code on the victim's computer through the internal ports and save the code on a web page which is later sent to the user.

LAW and Punishments

Cyber Law is a generic term which refers to all the legal and regulatory aspects of Internet and the World Wide Web.

The Information Technology Act, 2000 as amended by the Information Technology (amendment) Act, 2008 has been enforced on 27.10.2008. The act provides legal framework to address various types of cybercrimes and prescribes punishment also such crimes.

Hacking is explained in section 43 of the Information Technology Act, 2000. It includes unauthorized access, download, introducing virus, disrupting or damaging computers of others. And it is punishable under section 66 read with section 43 of the Information Technology Act, 2000. Forgery of electronic records, E-mail spoofing Under ITA 2008 Section 66A, 66C.

Sec. 66: Punishment for hacking with computer system. (This section has since been amended)

Whoever with the intent to cause or knowing that he is likely to cause wrongful loss or damage to the public or any person destroys or delete or alters any information residing in a computer resource or diminishes its value or utility or affects it injuriously by any means, commits hack.

Section 66A: Punishment for sending offensive messages through communication service, etc.

Any electronic mail or electronic mail message for the purpose of causing annoyance or inconvenience or to deceive or to mislead the addressee or recipient about the origin of such messages (Inserted vide ITAA 2008) shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which may extend to two three years and with fine.

Under Information Technology (Amendment) Act, 2008, Section 417, 419, 463 & 465 of Indian Penal Code, 1860 is also applicable for computer and internet related crimes.

Social Engineering: People who gain access to an E-mail using social engineering can be booked under section 463 of IPC. Punishment is 2 years jail and or fine.

Countermeasures of E-mail Hacking

The best solution for fighting against cybercrime is through education, enforcement of laws and highly developed security services. Technical expertise in online security is necessary, which can ensure that people of all the ages including children, teenagers, students, parents and business community are always safe. There are a number of general countermeasures that E-mail users must keep in mind while interacting with E-mail systems:

- It is extremely important for E-mail users to conduct proper awareness and training programs regarding the threats of E-mail. Unless all E-mail users are made aware of the security risks involved, it will be very difficult to successfully prevent any kind of E-mail fraud.
- A strong Antivirus tool should be used to scan all incoming and outgoing E-mails so as to provide immunity against any kind of virus or worm outbreak.
- A large number of E-mail viruses and worms spread on the Internet due to vulnerabilities in E-mail clients. Hence, it is advisable to constantly update our E-mail client to fix the known vulnerabilities.
- Don't trust even E-mails that you receive from your friends or colleagues. Sometimes, your friend or colleague's system gets infected with a virus and the malicious code automatically sends copies of itself to everybody in the address box.
- It is advisable to use a strong password for all E-mail accounts.
- Some people like to enter false contact information while registering a new E-mail account. Such a practice can sometimes prevent an attacker from cracking an E-mail account using the forget password attack.
- Always remain alert against any attempts of social engineering attacks.
- System administrators must disable the "mail relaying" option to prevent E-mail forging attacks on the Internet.
- One must remain aware of keyloggers that might have been installed on one's system to keep a track of all keystrokes that are being pressed.

Conclusion

Internet, being a global phenomenon is bound to attract many crimes such as E-mail crimes. India has taken a key step in prevention of Cyber Crimes by the enactment of the Information Technology Act and by giving exclusive powers to the police and other authorities to tackle such crimes.

Similar efforts have been made by various countries to fight E-Crime by enacting national legislations but in the long run, they may not prove to be as beneficial as desired. An effort is still wanted to formulate an international law on the use of Internet to control this looming danger of E-mail Crimes and to achieve a crime free Cyber Space. Prevention they say is the best cure. Cyber Laws aim to prevent cybercrimes through the use of penal provisions.

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